

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D6.6 — Common provenance model for processing biological material, data generation and computational workflows

WP6 – FAIRification and Provenance Services

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Executive Summary

The exchange of research data and physical specimens has become an issue of major importance for modern research. Many reports indicate problems with quality, trustworthiness, and reproducibility of research results, mainly due to poor documentation of the data generation or the collection of specimens. The significant impact of flawed research results on health, economics, and political decisions has frequently been stated. Consequently, professional societies and research initiatives call for improved and standardised documentation of the data and specimens used in research studies.

Provenance information is information about the history of an object, and depending on its content, it can be used to verify the quality and reliability of research results. In particular, provenance has been adopted in scientific domains to support a traceable lineage of research objects, such as biological material, data, or workflows. The purpose of provenance information is not to replace existing logging infrastructures or information systems that currently handle documentation of research objects and related processes or their metadata. Provenance information serves as long-term available information that can be typically used to assess the quality of the documented object (fitness for purpose) or to reproduce documented processes.

As the research objects are typically exchanged between organisations, each organisation can provide provenance information only about a portion of the documented research object's life cycle. WP6 in the EOSC-Life Project aimed to design a paradigm to capture and exchange interoperable provenance information, creating a common ground across different domains in the Life Sciences and building a harmonised understanding of provenance information. The work led to the definition of the **Common Provenance Model (CPM)**, described in Deliverable 6.2, starting with the design of components of distributed provenance information to enable interlinking of provenance information generated in different organisations involved in the research process, such as biobanks, research centres, universities, or analytical laboratories. As detailed in Deliverable 6.2, this distributed provenance information model builds on an existing provenance information standard, W3C PROV, and follows a general provenance composition pattern.

This document summarises the evolution of the work previously described in D6.2 and presents the CPM for processing biological material, data generation, and computational workflows. The CPM is designed to address the reproducibility issues in sciences by supporting the traceability of documented research objects in multi-organisational environments. This document is focused on, but not limited to, provenance of research objects, such as datasets, biological or environmental specimens, computational models, software, tools, or experimental results. The CPM supports reproducibility by providing a conceptual foundation for trustworthy provenance information, where each of its parts is generated, stored, and managed by a different organisation. In particular, the CPM defines a common horizontal framework to represent links between the provenance parts, and to represent common semantics to bind domain-specific provenance information.

The CPM serves as an open conceptual foundation for the development of the *ISO 23494 – Provenance information model for biological material and data* standard series.

Objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a. Objective 1: Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources for cloud use
 - The deliverable describes the application of an interoperable common provenance model to biological material handling, data generation, and data processing. This is undergoing standardisation as ISO 23494 Parts 2 and 3.
- b. Objective 2: Create an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC
 - The deliverable describes the application of an interoperable common provenance model to biological material handling, data generation, and data processing. This is undergoing standardisation as ISO 23494 Parts 2 and 3.
- c. Call objective: Proposals will address the stewardship of data handled by the involved research infrastructures according to the FAIR principles.
- d. Call objective: This will include the definition of domain specific data policies (e.g. acquisition, deposit, curation, preservation, access, sharing and re-use) and address any legislative or interoperability issues which affect data handling across geographical and discipline borders.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

The following sections outline the open specifications developed to model provenance information in the Life Sciences.

The first section is dedicated to general notions of the CPM, those always relevant in all possible use cases. After a quick summary of the basic elements of the CPM (already described in D6.2), the text introduces foundational concepts for navigating the distributed provenance, illustrates the versioning mechanism, the proposed strategy to deal with Persistent Identifiers [Valle2020], the support for integrity, authenticity, non-repudiation and confidentiality objects.

Section 2, Section 3, and Section 4 describe the results obtained in the definition of the CPM for biological material, data generation and data processing, the latter considered in the specific context of computational workflows.

Section 5 explains the relationship between the open specifications and the *ISO 23494 – Provenance information model for biological material and data* standard series.

Appendices 1 and 2 provide examples of the usage of the CPM to document two complex real-world use cases (digital pathology pipeline and acquisition and processing of biological material), while Appendix 3 shows how the CPM components are mapped to the EMBRC provenance model, which was developed as part of the EOSC-Life WP6 T6.4, to allow adoption of the CPM in the domain of marine biology.

1. The Common Provenance Model for Processing Biological Material, Data Generation and Computational Workflows

This section starts the description of the CPM by introducing the underlying PROV-DM¹ provenance model. Then, it presents how distributed provenance information is created, represented, and traversed. Finally, the section describes the proposed mechanism for provenance information versioning, dealing with missing provenance components, use of persistent identifiers, and support for provenance confidentiality, integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation of origin.

1.1. Provenance Information Representation

The CPM is an extension of the PROV-DM provenance model (Figure 1). The provenance information is represented as a graph data structure with annotated nodes and edges. The nodes represent *entities*, *activities*, or *agents*, and the edges represent their mutual relations such as *derivation*, *usage*, *generation*, or *attribution*. The nodes and edges are referred to as *provenance structures*. Each provenance structure can be represented in provenance by one or more *provenance statements*. The CPM defines types of nodes which are a specialisation of the nodes defined in the PROV-DM. The specialisation is realised using `prov:type` attribute², which is a standardised way of PROV-DM to add further typing information to provenance structures.

Figure 1: Conceptual structure of the W3C PROV-DM provenance model. Figure adapted from [Belhajjame2013] and cited from [Wittner2022].

Every provenance structure can be identified with an identifier. Stipulated by the PROV-DM, the provenance structures identifier has the form of a qualified name³.

1.2. Distributed Provenance Information

Distributed provenance information is created when a documented research object or its derivatives is exchanged across multiple organisations (or organisational units), and each of the organisations can provide provenance information only about a part of the documented objects

¹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-dm-20130430/>

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/#term-attribute-type>

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/#concept-qualifiedName>

life cycle. The exchanged object appears as an output of the **sender's** process, and as an input of the **receiver's** process. The corresponding provenance information is encapsulated in a **provenance component** (technically implemented as a PROV bundle⁴). Linking these provenance components forms possibly **distributed provenance chains**. A provenance chain is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scheme of a provenance chain. PI in the figure stands for “provenance information”. The figure is cited from [Wittner2022].

The CPM stipulates that the namespace used as part of a provenance structure identifier uniquely identifies the organisation that is responsible for provenance information generation.

1.3. Finalised Provenance Information

The **provenance finalisation event** is an instant in time when the available information from logging infrastructure of information systems is translated and managed according to the CPM. The resulting **finalised provenance information** is considered as an *immutable* snapshot of the current knowledge that is available at a given time instance. The provenance finalisation event may occur at the end of a documented process, on request, or periodically. The finalised provenance information cannot be modified directly, but any updates may be performed using the prescribed provenance versioning mechanism.

1.4. Provenance Backbone

According to the CPM, each provenance component consists of two types of information:

1. **Traversal information.** The traversal information contains location and other information about preceding/current/consecutive provenance components of a chain, so it can be used as a signpost to navigate through the chain itself. The semantics of the traversal

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/#component4>

information is common for all processes documented by the CPM – it is a mapping between inputs and related outputs of a documented process. In particular, the structure of the traversal information is defined in the CPM, so that the algorithms processing a provenance chain may rely on this common underlying structure.

2. **Domain/process specific information.** The domain/process specific information contains relevant details about the history of the process or object (digital or physical) described in the provenance component. The type of semantics of this specific information is always specific to the reference domain of the documented process/object. The CPM prescribes how the domain specific provenance is attached to the traversal information in a standardised way, and provides general requirements related to representation of common aspects of diverse domains (e.g., how to represent links to documentation outside finalised provenance).

Provenance backbone is the part of a provenance chain that corresponds to the union of traversal information that is present in components of a provenance chain (Figure 3). The CPM prescribes the structure of the underlying provenance graph that represents the traversal information, and provenance backbone consequently. This Deliverable D6.6 describes how the CPM defines semantics of nodes and edges present on the backbone.

Figure 3: Simplified schema of a provenance chain. Each component of the chain (here Bundle 1, etc.) consists of the traversal information and domain specific information. A provenance backbone is formed by traversal information present in distinct provenance components. Figure cited from [Wittner2022].

1.5. CPM Types for Provenance Backbone

The CPM defines types of provenance structures summarised in Table 1. The following types shall not be used in the domain specific provenance. The following types are defined in the CPM namespace⁵.

⁵ <http://commonprovenancemodel.org/ns/cpm/>

Provenance structure type	Semantics	Usage	Relation to PROV-DM
<code>currentConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents the exchanged object at the time of its receipt by a receiver.	The <code>currentConnector</code> contains links to metadata about the provenance components in which the connector is present.	The <code>currentConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:currentConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>backwardConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents a snapshot of the exchanged object at the time of its sending from a sender to a receiver.	The <code>backwardConnector</code> type is present in the receiver's provenance information, and contains information about the previous component of the chain. Identifier of the <code>backwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>forwardConnector</code> (having the prefix of the sender).	The <code>backwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:backwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>forwardConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents a snapshot of the exchanged object at the time of its sending from a sender to a receiver.	The <code>forwardConnector</code> type is present in the sender's provenance information, and contains information about the consecutive component of the chain. Identifier of the <code>forwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>backwardConnector</code> (having the prefix of the sender).	The <code>forwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:forwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>receiptActivity</code>	A PROV activity that represents how output of the previous process (<code>backwardConnector</code>) became an input for the current process (<code>currentConnector</code>).		The <code>receiptActivity</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:activity</code> , written as <code>activity(id, [prov:type='cpm:receiptActivity'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>mainActivity</code>	A PROV activity that represents how input of the current process (<code>currentConnector</code>)		The <code>mainActivity</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:activity</code> , written as <code>activity(id,</code>

	became an output of the current process (<code>forwardConnector</code>).		[<code>prov:type='cpm:mainActivity'</code>]) in PROV-N notation.
<code>senderAgent</code>	A PROV agent that represents responsibility for the preceding step in the chain.		The <code>senderAgent</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:agent</code> , written as <code>agent(id, [prov:type='cpm:senderAgent'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>receiverAgent</code>	A PROV agent that represents responsibility for the consecutive step in the chain.		The <code>receiverAgent</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:agent</code> , written as <code>agent(id, [prov:type='cpm:receiverAgent'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>jumpForwardConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents an output of a process, whose derivatives are used in a non-adjacent consecutive step.	The <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> type is present in the sender's provenance information and contains information about one of the consecutive but "non-adjacent" components of the chain. Identifier of the corresponding <code>jumpBackwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> .	The <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:jumpForwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>jumpBackwardConnector</code>	A PROV entity that represents an object from which an input of the described process was derived, and which is coming from a non-adjacent previous step.	The <code>jumpBackwardConnector</code> type is present in the receiver's provenance information, and contains information about one of the preceding but "non-adjacent" components of the chain. Identifier of the corresponding <code>jumpForwardConnector</code> is the same as the identifier of the respective <code>jumpBackwardConnector</code> .	The <code>jumpBackwardConnector</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:jumpBackwardConnector'])</code> in PROV-N notation.

Table 1: A list of the CPM types which form the basis of traversal information and provenance backbone of a provenance chain.

Merging the two components of the chain that contain connectors with the shared identifier results in a provenance graph that is the result of pasting the two subgraphs (present in the individual components) along the node with the shared identifier.

Depending on the connector type, each connector contains information required to query the content of the preceding/consecutive component of the chain. In particular, each connector must contain

- Identifier of a respective provenance component.
- URL of a service, where content of a provenance component with a given identifier can be requested.

This is exemplified in Figure 4. Another mechanism for linking provenance components which is built on the top of Persistent Identifiers is described later in this document.

Figure 4: A schema of forwardConnector and backwardConnector usage. The figure is adapted⁶ from [Wittner2022].

1.6. Provenance Backbone Structure

Provenance backbone is represented in finalised provenance information as a provenance graph with prescribed structure. The structure is depicted in Figure 5. The structure of the backbone is following:

- The receiptActivity activity uses (prov:used) backwardConnector entities and generates (prov:wasGeneratedBy) currentConnector entities. Each pair of currentConnector and respective backwardConnector is related using derivation (prov:wasDerivedFrom) relation if and only if the particular currentConnector was somehow affected by the backwardConnector.
- The receiptActivity activity invalidates (prov:wasInvalidatedBy) the backwardConnector entities.
- The mainActivity activity uses (prov:used) the currentConnector entities and generates (prov:wasGeneratedBy) forwardConnector entities. Each pair of currentConnector and respective forwardConnector is related using derivation

⁶ Figures that depict various connector types were adapted to use forwardConnector, backwardConnector, and currentConnector types. The academic publication [Wittner2022] where the concepts have been presented use names of the connector types which are already deprecated. The semantics of connectors was preserved.

(`prov:wasDerivedFrom`) relation if and only if the particular `forwardConnector` was somehow affected by the `currentConnector`.

- `backwardConnector` entity is attributed (`prov:wasAttributedTo`) to `receiverAgent`.
- `forwardConnector` entity is attributed (`prov:wasAttributedTo`) to `senderAgent`.

Figure 5: Provenance graph structure of the traversal information. Figure adapted from [Wittner2022].

Domain specific information is attached to the traversal information by application of the Compound Activities Pattern [Moreau2013]. Technically, the main and the receipt activities contain an attribute (`dct:hasPart`) listing sub-activities which the respective activity consists of. Inputs and outputs of the activities and sub-activities are related using the PROV specialisation relation. The pattern is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Schema of the traversal information with the domain specific provenance information attached to it. Agents are omitted for simplicity. Figure adapted from [Wittner2022].

Linking of provenance components is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Interconnecting provenance components that contain the traversal information expressed according to the CPM. CC: current connector; BC: backward connector; FC: forward connector. Agents are omitted for simplicity. The figure is adapted from [Wittner2022].

In order to achieve the privacy of humans (e.g., patients, or donors of biological material), a distributed provenance chain may be intentionally interrupted by cutting out related connectors. In such scenarios, the link can be completely non-existent, or it can be preserved outside of finalised information, so that traceability of origin of biological material still exists in cases when disputes about origin of derived data arise (the link can be then, for instance, provided to an authority). In the first scenario, traceability of the source of the data will be unattainable.

1.7. Missing Provenance Components

The CPM provides means to deal with missing provenance components of a provenance chain. This may happen, for instance, when an organisation responsible for the management and storage of finalised provenance information ceases to exist. The CPM addresses such scenarios by providing two additional types of connectors – `jumpForwardConnector` and `jumpBackwardConnector` – which enable linking of provenance components documenting “non-adjacent” processes. Semantics of the jump connectors was summarised in Table 1. The usage of the connectors is following:

- `jumpForwardConnector` is derived from the corresponding `currentConnector`.
- `currentConnector` is derived from the `jumpBackwardConnector`.

Figures 8 and 9 depicts, respectively, a missing provenance component and the usage of the jump connectors with the provenance backbone.

Figure 8: Schema of a provenance chain with a missing provenance component. Agents are omitted for simplicity. Figure adapted from [Wittner2022].

Figure 9: Schema of a provenance chain with a missing provenance component, and addressing this scenario using the jump connectors. Agents are omitted for simplicity. Figure adapted from [Wittner2022].

1.8. Provenance Components Versioning

Finalised provenance information can contain errors, and for that reason the CPM provides a mechanism to update finalised provenance information in a way which does not disrupt the integrity of the chain. The mechanism exploits the concept of meta-provenance, or provenance of provenance in other words. To update a provenance component, a new provenance component is created. The new provenance component can contain updated, additional, or reduced information. The original provenance component must be preserved since other provenance components may contain links to it.

The provenance versioning pattern is depicted in Figure 10. Both the new and the original components are expressed in meta-provenance as two distinct entities and are related using PROV Revision relation. In addition, both entities are related to an entity representing all the versions of a particular bundle using the PROV Specialization relation. The meta-provenance is encapsulated in a meta-component, technically implemented as a PROV bundle. Meta-provenance of different provenance components may be expressed in the same meta-component. Meta-provenance of a provenance component shall not be fragmented across different meta-components.

The pattern used to express different versions of a provenance component in a meta-component is an application of the revision pattern [Moreau2013]. The described semantics loosely follows the semantics described in the PAV (provenance, authoring and versioning) ontology [Ciccarese2013].

Figure 10: Expression of provenance component's versions in meta-provenance. Figure cited from [Wittner2022].

1.9. Using Persistent Identifiers for Connectors

Persistent identifier [Valle2020] (PID) is an identifier that is unique and resolvable in the long term. A general mechanism of PIDs usage as an identifier for a provenance structure was described in the previous deliverable on the CPM [Wittner2021].

In order to enable traversal of a provenance chain, the traversal algorithm needs to be provided with information about provenance components that are achievable from the component, which is currently being traversed. To achieve this, the CPM stipulates that each connector is identified with a PID, which is used to obtain required information. Depending on the type of the connector (*forwardConnector*, *backwardConnector*, or *currentConnector*), the corresponding PID resolves into the following information:

1. Identifier of the corresponding bundle, in which the connector is present.
 - a. For the *currentConnector*, the PID resolves to the “current” provenance component, in which the *currentConnector* is present.
 - b. For the *forwardConnector*, the PID resolves to the consecutive provenance component in the chain (analogously for the *jumpForwardConnector*).
 - c. For the *backwardConnector*, the PID resolves to the previous provenance component in the chain (analogously for the *jumpBackwardConnector*).
2. Identifier of the corresponding meta-bundle, in which meta-provenance about the corresponding bundle can be found.
3. The corresponding connector expressed in any serialisation, which might be subject of an underlying content negotiation protocol.

Finally, the CPM stipulates that provenance components identifiers are dereferenceable, i.e., dereferencing a component ID returns the content of the component (presuming proper authorization).

Based on this mechanism, the provenance chain traversal algorithm can navigate between provenance components using the following procedure:

1. Obtaining a connector PID as an input of the procedure.
2. Resolving the connector PID to get further information about the respective provenance component.
3. Dereferencing the respective component ID to get finalised provenance information stored in the component.
4. As the connector PID is shared between the components, the corresponding connector must be present in the obtained finalised provenance information. This entity then serves as a starting point for traversing the chain further.
5. Dereferencing the corresponding meta-bundle ID may be used to get further meta-provenance about the provenance component.

Alternatively, the corresponding component ID and meta-bundle ID might be present as an attribute of the connector (using the standard attributes list defined in W3C PROV). This would simplify and speed up traversing through the chain. The ability to dereference an ordinary ID is not guaranteed, however, unlike the case of the PIDs.

1.10. Support for Provenance Integrity, Authenticity and Non-repudiation

One of the main features of the finalised provenance information is that it is considered immutable once it is generated. As a consequence, cryptographic operations, such as hashing and digital signatures, can be applied to the finalised provenance information to achieve its integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation. The related cryptographic metadata (certificates, signature keys, hash values, etc.) can be expressed in corresponding meta-bundles. Verification procedures can be then applied during a provenance chain traversal, where PIDs used to identify connectors contain links to the corresponding meta-bundles. The versioning mechanism is designed in a way that it does not directly modify finalised provenance information, but rather creates a new copy of the finalised provenance component and relates the new version to the original one in a meta-bundle. This way, integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation can be achieved for all versions of a provenance component. As the versioning mechanism does not modify the original components, the integrity of provenance chains is also not disrupted.

A non-repudiation policy for distributed provenance information

Non-repudiation is a strong version of authenticity [Shirey2007]. While authenticity provides us with guarantees that a piece of data is coming from a purported source, the non-repudiation provides us with guarantees that the purported source can not deny the origin. This is achieved by providing an undeniable proof of the origin which is verifiable by a third party. However, in order to achieve non-repudiation, the management of evidence related to finalised provenance information integrity and authenticity must be designed in advance [Roe2010]. In particular, non-repudiation can be only achieved within the context of a clearly defined security policy for a particular application and legal environment [ISO2009].

To help address this challenge, a set of rules to achieve non-repudiable finalised provenance information was developed. The rules were created by adoption of general requirements for

irrefutable evidence [Menezes1996] to provenance⁷:

- **General requirement 1:** The authenticity and integrity of finalised provenance need to be established, such that its alleged author cannot later deny that authenticity.
- **General requirement 2:** A verifier must be able to verify the authenticity and integrity properties of finalised provenance information.
- **General requirement 3:** Authenticity and integrity verification information must be available during a pre-defined period of time, according to a time period for which non-repudiation should be achieved (to do so for an unlimited period, if feasible, is likely to be expensive, due to the long-term costs of managing the evidence, replacing cryptographic keys after their expiration, and adapting to new threats).
- **General requirement 4:** Responsibilities and rules related to finalised provenance generation, storage, and verification must be defined in order to enable all participating parties to behave responsibly, in accordance with these rules. Violating these rules can lead to decreased trust in the system.
- **General requirement 5:** If a dispute related to the origin of finalised provenance occurs, trusted timestamps are required to reconstruct past events.

To address the general requirements, the following rules related to finalised provenance information generation and management are defined. Each rule is accompanied with a brief rationale.

1. The sender must digitally sign the finalised provenance information.
 - *Authenticity and integrity of the finalised provenance are achieved by this rule.*
2. All related cryptographic operations must be performed using a special piece of hardware, which provides additional protection against private key disclosure.
 - *Applying this rule reduces risk of provenance falsification by establishing additional protection of the keys.*
3. The sender should define a certain amount of time (*clearance period* [Menezes1996]) to report a confidentiality violation of the private key used for digital signatures creation.
 - *This rule provides additional trust in confidentiality of private keys.*
4. A timestamp referring to the creation of finalised provenance information must be generated by a third party.
 - *This rule provides additional trust in reconstructed events, especially if a signing key had been revoked or expired before a dispute arose.*
5. The sender can not be the only party responsible for storing and maintaining the evidence related to finalised provenance information integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation verification.
 - *This rule provides additional protection of the evidence, mainly in cases when the sender has a motivation to disrupt or destroy the evidence (e.g., in cases when finalised provenance information contains evidence that could potentially harm the sender).*
6. The evidence should be stored in a way which prevents its modification.
 - *This rule provides additional trust in the evidence integrity and authenticity.*

⁷ The requirements and the rules were initially published as part of an academic publication [Fairweather2021]. The rules provided in this deliverable are generalisation of the policy which was developed for a particular system. The text of the requirements and rules was adopted from the publication.

7. After finalised provenance information is generated and provided to a receiver, the receiver must verify its meaningfulness, authenticity, and integrity.
 - *A presumption for this rule is that non-repudiation of the finalised provenance is in the best interest of the receiver, as the receiver will typically make a decision based on the information stored in the provided finalised provenance information.*
8. Finalised provenance information and meta-provenance must contain all relevant timestamps, such as when the finalised provenance information was generated, or when it was provided to a receiver.
 - *Inclusion of the timestamps enables and simplifies past events reconstruction.*

1.11. Support for Opaque Provenance Information

Presence of opaque provenance information is necessary to hide confidential information from non-authorized users. The CPM provides two general methods to support confidentiality of information present in finalised provenance information:

1. **Intentional interruption of a provenance chain.** In general, some components of a provenance chain may be considered more sensitive than others, as a consequence of the nature of information stored in a provenance component⁸. If necessary, a provenance chain can be intentionally broken by removing links to sensitive components of the chain. As the versioning mechanism enables having multiple versions of a component, different versions of a component can differ in inclusion of the connectors. As a result, proper authorization mechanisms can be used to disclose the links to sensitive components to authorised users, and to hide the links to sensitive components for users without proper authorisation.
2. **Access control management on a provenance graph pattern level.** The traversal information included in finalised provenance information is designed in a way that it minimises occurrence of sensitive information on the provenance backbone. As a provenance chain traversal algorithm operates primarily on the backbone, the amount of sensitive information which the algorithm would need to come in contact with is minimised, resulting in alignment with the *least privilege principle* [Saltzer1975]. In particular, the traversal algorithm may not be allowed to traverse to the domain specific part of a provenance component exploiting the fact that the domain specific part of finalised provenance information is attached to the backbone using a specific type of relation.

2. Biological Material Provenance Information

Biological Material Provenance Information provides types of provenance structures which are common for various areas of biological material handling. The proposed model can be then used as a groundwork for the development of extensions of a complete model describing biological material processing, combining the general structures with specialised contents, focused on domain/material-type/use-case specific requirements (see Appendix 3). The types of Biological Material Provenance Information are summarised in Table 2.

⁸ For instance, finalised provenance information documenting acquisition of a biological material from a patient or a donor poses higher confidentiality (or privacy) risks than finalised provenance information documenting application of an analytical tool to an anonymised dataset.

The types will be defined in the `pbm` namespace⁹.

Provenance structure type	Semantics	Relation to PROV-DM
<code>sample</code>	A PROV entity that represents a biological or environmental sample.	The <code>sample</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:sample'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>container</code>	A PROV entity that represents a container.	The <code>container</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:container'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>device</code>	A PROV entity that represents a processing or storage device for specimens.	The <code>device</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:device'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>reagent</code>	A PROV entity that represents a reagent.	The <code>reagent</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:reagent'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>sop</code>	A PROV entity that represents a standard operating procedure.	The <code>sop</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:sop'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>source</code>	A PROV entity that represents a source of a sample.	The <code>source</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:entity</code> , written as <code>entity(id, [prov:type='pbm:source'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>distributionActivity</code>	A PROV activity that represents distribution or disposal of a sample.	The <code>distributionActivity</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:activity</code> , written as <code>activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:distributionActivity'])</code> in PROV-N notation.
<code>retrievalActivity</code>	A PROV activity that represents retrieval of a sample from sample storage.	The <code>retrieval</code> is a specialisation of <code>prov:activity</code> , written as <code>activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:retrievalActivity'])</code> in PROV-N notation.

⁹ <http://commonprovenancemodel.org/ns/pbm/>

storageActivity	A PROV activity that represents storage of a sample.	The storageActivity is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:storageActivity']) in PROV-N notation.
processingActivity	A PROV activity that represents processing of a sample.	The processingActivity is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:processingActivity']) in PROV-N notation.
receivmentActivity	A PROV activity that represents receivment of a sample.	The receivmentActivity is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:receivmentActivity']) in PROV-N notation.
transportActivity	A PROV activity that represents transport of a sample.	The transportActivity is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:transportActivity']) in PROV-N notation.
acquisitionActivity	A PROV activity that represents acquisition of a sample	The acquisitionActivity is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as activity(id, [prov:type='pbm:acquisitionActivity']) in PROV-N notation.

Table 2: A list of provenance structure types to express semantics common for various areas of biological material handling.

The usage of the Provenance Information Model for Biological Material types is exemplified in the Appendix 2.

3. Data Generation Provenance Information

Data generation techniques include a wide scope of areas, such as optical microscopy, or DNA sequencing. The CPM stipulates that a data generation step is documented in a single provenance component, as the data generation can not be passed to another organisation during the data generation process. A provenance chain may document multiple data generation steps. The CPM defines the `cpm:dataGeneration` type, which must be present as a type of the `mainActivity` in the traversal information part of the component. The type is listed in Table 3.

Provenance structure name	Semantics	Relation to PROV-DM
dataGeneration	A PROV activity that represents a data generation.	The dataGeneration is a specialisation of prov:activity, written as entity(id, [prov:type='cpm:dataGeneration']) in PROV-N notation.

Table 3: Data generation type.

The usage of the dataGeneration activity type is exemplified in the Appendix 1.

4. Provenance Information Model for Data Processing with Computational Workflows

Computational workflows were the first technique, among a broad spectrum of approaches, to be considered when the specifications for data processing were developed, since their usage is very common in different domains in the life sciences [Cohen-Boulakia2017, Garijo2014, Shade2015]. RO-Crates is currently the favoured way to pack workflow execution-related artefacts into a single research object. The CPM was integrated with the RO-Crate as part of informal collaboration with the BY-COVID project, where specific profiles for documentation of computational workflow execution are being developed. One of these profiles is CPM RO-Crate profile¹⁰, which enables embedding and identification of the CPM provenance files into an RO-Crate.

5. Relation to the ISO 23494 Standard Series

The CPM aims to be adopted by both academia and industry. Collaboration with academic and scientific communities is established through the EOSC-Life project. Collaboration with industrial partners is established through involvement of the BBMRI-ERIC in ISO TC 276 (Biotechnology) WG5 (Data processing integration). In particular, the CPM will be published and maintained as an open technical specification, which was the result of the EOSC-Life project. The public model is adopted by the ISO WG, where it serves as an open conceptual foundation for related provenance standard series development.

The current stage of the series standardisation is following:

1. *ISO/TS 23494-1 Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements* has been published in April 2023. The document specifies the general concept of provenance information for biological material, data generation, and data processing, and sets general requirements on provenance information management.

¹⁰ <https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate/0.2>

2. *ISO 23494-2 Provenance information model for biological material and data – Part 2: Common Provenance Model* has undergone the Preliminary Work Item stage of ISO the standard development process and was proposed to become a New Work Item Proposal in July 2023. The document sets requirements on technical aspects of the CPM.
3. *ISO 23494-3 Provenance information model for biological material and data – Part 3: Provenance of Biological Material* will be submitted to the ISO WG requesting opening of the Preliminary Work Item stage of the ISO standard development process. In the context of the series, ISO 23494-3 is a vertical standard built on the top of the ISO 23494-2. In a broader context, ISO 23494-3 will serve as a horizontal standard for domain-/material-type specific standards that are anticipated to appear in future. The document sets requirements specific for provenance information specific for biological material.

Additionally, another 3 parts of the provenance standard series are anticipated in future:

1. *ISO 23494-4 Provenance information model for biological material and data – Part 4: Provenance of Data Generation*. The document will set requirements specific for provenance information of data generation techniques, such as sequencing, spectrometry, microscopy, etc.
2. *ISO 23494-5 Provenance information model for biological material and data – Part 5: Provenance of Data Processing*. The document will set requirements specific for provenance information of computational aspects of life sciences, such as the execution of computational workflows.
3. *ISO 23494-6 Provenance information model for biological material and data – Part 6: Security Extensions*. The document will set security-related requirements to achieve authenticity, integrity, and non-repudiation of finalised provenance information.

Further description of the standard series and the standardisation process is available in a recent publication [Wittner2023].

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Abbreviations

CPM Common Provenance Model

PID Persistent Identifier

PROV-DM The PROV data model, a generic data model for provenance

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Deliverable D6.6 has been delivered according to the contractual schedule (August 2023).

Adjustments

Adjustments made: None

Appendices

Appendix 1 CPM for a Digital Pathology Use Case

This appendix demonstrates and explains the usage of the CPM to document a complex real-world example from the digital pathology domain. The goal of the demonstration is to show how the traversal information is designed for distinct provenance components of a chain, and how domain specific provenance is attached to the traversal information. For that purpose, the use case is described, and application of the CPM is explained for each step of the use case individually.

The demonstration was published as a supplementary material for the CPM academic publication [Wittner2022]. The text and the figures presented in this Appendix are citations or adaptations of the text which was originally published as the supplementary material.

The figures presented in this appendix contain provenance graphs drawn according to W3C PROV conventions. However, the figures are simplified for clarity, and do not contain prefixes of identifiers of provenance structures or their attributes.

General Description of the Use Case

The example considers a use case from the Digital pathology domain specialised in the detection of prostate cancer¹¹. Its goal is to train an AI model to detect presence of carcinogenic cells in Whole Slide Images of human prostate, which have been acquired in a clinical environment.

The whole process consists of several steps, each of which is carried out by different organisations, or different organisational units of the same organisation. General schema of resulting provenance information documenting the process is depicted in Figure A.1.1.

1. Biological material acquisition is done in a clinical environment. Primary samples are taken as part of a medical treatment – prostate biopsy – and sent to a pathological department for examination.
2. Biological material processing, WSI generation and examination are done as part of the diagnostic process. This consists of the gross evaluation, generation of tissue blocks, cutting of tissue blocks into slices to be placed on glass slides, staining and scanning. Resulting scans (whole slide images (WSIs) of the slides) are consecutively examined and annotated by a pathologist. The annotations depict tumour areas and other morphological features. The annotated scans, resulting diagnosis and the slides are then sent to a biobank to be stored. The annotated scans are provided to an AI based computational workflow.
3. Biological material storage. The samples are stored in a controlled environment and provided through a searchable database for future use. Thereby a specific cohort or a set of samples can be collected to answer designated research questions.

¹¹ Digital pathology is a research field applying achievements in imaging technologies to develop systems capable of diagnosing or supporting diagnosis of patients based on their clinical data and large scans of histopathological biological material (so called Whole Slide Images, WSIs), also enabling the application of AI methodologies to improve the evaluation results.

4. WSI pre-processing prepares the annotated scans to be processed by an AI model. Since the AI model is not capable of processing high resolution images, the images are split into smaller pieces –patches – and corresponding annotations transformed into appropriate format. The resulting dataset is divided into two parts - training and testing sets.
5. AI model training. Training part of the AI workflow consists of consuming the annotated images (training set) and training an AI model to identify tumours on the WSIs. Result of this step is a trained AI model and a summary file containing the AI model predictions about tumour presence.
6. AI model testing. The trained AI model is used to identify carcinogenic cells at whole slide images, present in the testing set (WSIs in the testing set has not been used during training). The result is compared with the pathologist's annotations. In this step, it is possible to estimate the quality of the predictions made by the pipeline either to modify it to get better results, or to declare that it satisfies given requirements and can therefore potentially be used in clinical use or research.

Figure A.1.1: Simplified schema of the distributed provenance chain for the digital pathology research pipeline. The figure is cited from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Digital Material Handling and Digitization

Biological Material Acquisition

Beginning of the pipeline starts with a patient in a surgical department of a hospital from whom a biological sample is extracted. Patients are associated with an identifier, which is unique across given country (in countries like Czech Republic or nordic countries). A bioptic request is generated for the patient, which serves as a prescription for the acquisition of biological material from the patient and its consecutive examination. Result of the acquisition process is biological material which is sent to a pathology department of the same institute.

Provenance component depicted in Figure A.1.2 represents the beginning of a distributed provenance chain. The provenance backbone does not contain backwardConnector,

receiptActivity nor a currentConnector, since there is no previous step in this example, which would be documented by finalised provenance information. For that reason, the start of the chain is expressed on the backbone as a main activity, which generates the forwardConnector, representing the acquired sample.

If there would be a previous step documenting the sample source – e.g., finalised provenance information documenting patient related clinical data using HL7 FHIR4 – this would be linked using the backward connector, receipt activity and current connector provenance structures as defined in the proposed provenance model.

The forward connector entity is present on the provenance backbone, despite finalised provenance information documenting the consecutive step does not necessarily exist during the finalisation event for the current step. Semantics of presence of the forward connector is that it explicitly says that there was an output of the documented process, which was provided to an external consecutive process – this says nothing about whether finalisation event for the consecutive step has already happened, so that it says nothing about whether provenance information about the next step exists, or whether the next step was already performed. In such a case, the attributes of the forward connector (destination bundle identifier and provenance service URI) used for the forward navigation would stay empty. In case when the finalisation event for the consecutive step is executed later, the technical attributes of the connector to locate the consecutive provenance component can be added using the proposed versioning mechanism. This is the same for all parts of the chain.

Figure A1.2: Finalised provenance information documenting sample acquisition. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Biological Material Processing, WSI Generation and Examination

Based on the same bioptic request, the biological material goes to a pathology department, to perform the biological material preparation, scanning and examination. This consists of the following steps:

1. Macroscopy: pathologist decides which parts of the material will be further processed. These parts are split, fixed in formalin, and embedded into paraffin. Results are blocks with fixed samples (small tissue parts).
2. Slicing: the blocks are cut into slices, which are put onto glass slides.

3. Staining: the slides are stained according to a standardised staining protocol. Different slides can be stained according to different protocols (depending on purpose), possibly at different places, these can be later collected together to continue the process
4. Digitization process/scanning: using a slide scanner, whole slide images of the slides are generated.
5. Digital pathology examination: pathologist takes WSIs and examines them on his/her computer, trying to identify cancer structures, producing annotations of those structures.

Physical slides along the WSIs and pathological diagnosis are then sent to and stored in the biobank. WSIs with annotation are sent for integration into dataset used in an AI pipeline.

Finalised provenance information for this step, depicted in Figure A1.3., contains a single backward connector and a derived current connector entity. These two entities represent the sample received from the previous step. The sample is then used by the main activity (physical slide preparation), which generates three different types of outputs – pathological diagnoses, resulting slides collection and WSI data (scans and annotations). All of these are sent to a biobank for storage in the consecutive step. A copy of the WSI data is sent to a high-performance computing centre to train the AI models, which is expressed on the backbone as a standalone entity.

Biological Material Storage

The slides, pathological diagnosis and WSI annotations from the digital pathology step are received and stored in biobank and can be later requested for further use. For the purpose of the example, processes related to biological material handling and processing ends here. Finalised provenance information for the samples' storage step is depicted in Figure A.1.4.

The provenance backbone in the finalised provenance information contains three backward connectors, each of them corresponding to the outputs of the previous process. The pathological diagnosis and WSI data are merged into a single entity during the receipt activity since there was no reason to express those as standalone entities¹².

The main activity – storage process – does not generate any outputs on the provenance backbone. This is because the outputs of this process (stored samples) have not been sent to any consecutive process yet.

The reason for generating finalised provenance example, despite it has no traceable outputs, is that the stored samples might be requested after long time (generally in years) and there is a need to finalise (and consequently digitally sign and archive) particular provenance information without further waiting (not signing provenance information would leave a space for potential malicious tampering with generated provenance). If the biological material would be requested for further use later, the generated provenance component could be updated using the versioning mechanism.

¹² the reason for splitting the entities in the previous step was that the WSI data are sent to the AI pipeline without the pathological diagnosis.

Figure A1.3: Finalised provenance information documenting sample processing, whole slide images generation and their examination. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824087.

Figure A.1.4: Finalised provenance information documenting sample storage. The figure is adapted from [Wittner2022].

Data Processing and Machine Learning Pipeline

The machine learning pipeline (MLP) processes annotated images of slides and learns to detect the presence of carcinoma. The pipeline is implemented as a set of python scripts and is executed on a server at a high-performance computing centre. The input dataset is stored on a filesystem, where it is accessed by the scripts.

WSI Dataset Pre-processing

In this step of the research pipeline, the WSIs coming from the previous step are collected and pre-processed. Purpose of the pre-processing step is to split the WSIs into smaller regions – patches – to make them appropriate for the consecutive AI model training. The patches are also divided into two datasets: training and testing. Patches, which form WSIs in the testing dataset can never be included in the validation or training dataset, since this would disrupt the whole AI model training process. Finalised provenance information documenting the WSIs pre-processing is depicted in Figure A.1.5.

WSIs are expressed on provenance backbone as a current connector received by a receipt activity and derived from a connector, linking the current bundle to the previous step. The current connector is then used by the main activity, which generates two entities representing training and testing sets represented as forward connectors.

Figure A.1.6: Finalised provenance information documenting AI model training. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

AI Model Testing

Goal of the AI model testing step is to estimate how good the model is with predictions of tumour presence in given WSIs. In contrast with the previous step, where the validation steps were evaluated according to patches annotations, the testing part is evaluated according to the whole slide images. This is done by running the model on the testing dataset, and its results are then compared with the original annotations from the pathologists. In this part of the research pipeline, the AI model does not have the original annotations as part of the input - is it the task of the trained model to determine whether and where the carcinogenic parts of slides are present. Result of this step is a statistic providing qualitative assessment of the trained model results. The resulting finalised provenance information is depicted in Figure A.1.7.

Figure A.1.7: Finalised provenance information documenting AI model testing. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

This is the last step of the pipeline described in this example. As a result, the main activity does not generate any outputs – forward connectors – which would enable navigation to finalised provenance information documenting a consecutive step (simply because there is no consecutive step). For that reason, every output of this process is expressed only in a domain specific part of finalised provenance information.

Missing Provenance Components and Jump Connectors

The basic structure of a distributed provenance chain was shown (Figure A.1.1) in the previous sections. In this section, we will use the existing chain and the example to demonstrate usage of jump connectors — a method to address missing provenance components. The methods for missing provenance components can be used when a provenance part in a chain cease to exist (e.g., because a particular responsible organisation ceases to exist), when part of a chain is not generated at all, or to simplify traversal of the chain in cases, when some steps of the are not in primary interest.

Since attachment of domain specific provenance is not affected by including jump connectors, we omit domain specific provenance from figures for simplicity, and depict relevant parts of provenance backbone only.

Adding JumpBackward Connectors

The first bundles in the provenance chain containing a jump backward connector are documenting biological material storage and WSI data pre-processing steps. This is because

biological material acquisition step, and the second referring to the raw WSI data generated in the data generation step. This is depicted in Figure A.1.10.

Figure A.1.10: Provenance backbone for AI model training including two jump backward connectors. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

The last component of the provenance chain containing a jump backward connector is documenting the AI model testing process. This bundle contains two current connectors: the trained model coming from the AI model training step, and a test dataset coming from the data pre-processing step. Both inputs have the same predecessors, so they are derived from the same jump backward connectors: one representing acquired sample in the biological material step, and second representing WSI data generated in the data generation step. In addition, the current connector representing the trained model is derived from the jump backward connector representing the trained dataset, which was generated in the data pre-processing step. The resulting backbone is depicted in Figure A.1.11.

Figure A.1.11: Provenance backbone for AI model testing including three jump backward connectors. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Adding JumpForward Connectors

Jump connectors are entities with shared identifiers. For that reason, similarly to sender and backward connectors, jump backward connectors should have corresponding jump forward connectors in the referenced bundles. Jump forward connectors are included in four bundles in our example. Biological material acquisition bundle contains four jump forward connectors, each referring to a bundle, where derivatives of acquired biological material are used. In particular, the bundle contains a jump connector to refer to biological material storage step, WSI data pre-processing step, AI model training step and AI model testing step. Analogously, the material processing and data generation bundle contain jump forward connectors to refer to AI model training and testing steps. The WSI data pre-processing bundle contains a jump forward connector to refer to the AI model testing step. The resulting bundles with jump forward connectors included are depicted in Figure A.1.12, Figure A.1.13 and Figure A.1.14.

Figure A.1.12: Provenance backbone for biological sample acquisition including four jump forward connectors. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Figure A.1.13: Provenance backbone for samples processing and data generation step including two jump forward connectors. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Figure A.1.14: Provenance backbone for WSI data pre-processing step including both jump forward connectors and jump backward connector. The figure is adapted from the supplementary material of [Wittner2022].

Appendix 2 Biological Material Provenance for a Use Case

This appendix demonstrates and explains how to use Biological Material Provenance Information (Section 2) to document a biological material handling use case in finalised provenance information. For that purpose, the use case is described, and application of the CPM is explained for each step of the use case individually. Design of the provenance backbone is not explained in this appendix, as it was explained in Appendix 1.

The figures presented in this appendix contain provenance graphs drawn according to W3C PROV conventions. However, the figures are simplified for clarity, and do not contain prefixes of identifiers of provenance structures. In contrast to the previous appendix, the figures contain prefixes of provenance structure attributes, as these serve as the main point to refer to external ontologies.

The namespaces used in the examples are listed in Table 4¹³.

Prefix	Namespace	Description
obo	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/	A linked data server designed for ontologies
sphn	https://biomedit.ch/rdf/sphn-ontology/sphn#	The SPHN RDF Schema
snomed	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/SNOMEDCT/	SNOMED Clinical Terms
geosparql	http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#	A vocabulary for representing spatial information

¹³ The namespaces `cpm` and `pbm` were defined earlier in this document.

dct	http://purl.org/dc/terms/	DCMI Metadata Terms
foaf	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/	FOAF Vocabulary Specification

Table 4: Domain or area specific dictionaries and their namespaces used in the example of the biological material provenance.

General Description of the Use Case

The example considers a biological material handling use case. The use case consists of several steps, each of which is carried out by different organisations, or different organisational units of the same organisation. The use case consists of the following three steps:

1. Biological material acquisition is done in a clinical environment. Primary samples are taken from a patient and are sent to a pathological department for examination.
2. Biological material processing consisting of macroscopy, cutting of the acquired sample into slices to be placed on glass slides, and staining the slides. The resulting slides are transported to a biobank for storage.
3. Biological material storage. The sample is stored in a controlled environment and distributed to a user later.

Biological Material Acquisition

The pipeline starts with a patient in a surgical department of a hospital from whom a biological sample is extracted. Result of the acquisition process is biological material which is sent to a pathology department of the same institute.

The source of biological material – a patient – is expressed in provenance information as PROV entity of type `pbm:sourceEntity`. The reason for not expressing the patient as a PROV agent is that in this example, the patient does not bear any responsibility, which could be expressed by a PROV agent. Consent information related to the biological material acquisition is expressed as a PROV entity, which is related to the patient in the patient's entity `pbm:consentInformation` attribute. The fact that the patient is a human is expressed in the patient's entity `pbm:belongsToTaxonomy` attribute, using the `obo:NCIT_C14225` value referring to an external ontology.

The geographic location of where the sample has been acquired is expressed as the `pbm:atGeographicLocation` attribute of the sample acquisition activity typed with `pbm:acquisitionActivity` type. Further details about the location are expressed using a standalone PROV entity that expresses the location.

The result of the acquisition is a sample. The type of the sample and further details about its preservation are expressed using PROV type (`prov:type`), provenance of biological material (`pbm:hasContainerType`, `pbm:hasPreservation`), or external (`sphn:hasBodySite`) attributes.

The transportation of the sample to a pathology department is expressed as another PROV activity of type `pbm:transportationActivity`.

All the activities are associated with persons responsible for particular activities. Role of each person is expressed using the `prov:role` attribute of respective Association relation. Start times and end times of the activities are expressed using the `startTime` and `endTime` properties of respective PROV Activities.

The resulting finalised provenance information is depicted in Figure A2.1.

Biological Material Processing

The sample processing part of the example is done in a pathology department. The processing starts with receipt of the sample from the hospital, continues with macroscopy, cutting, and staining of the sample, and ends with transportation of the result sample to a biobank.

The receipt activity in the domain specific part of the finalised provenance information is expressed with `pbm:receivmentActivity` type. Macroscopy activity is expressed with the `snomed:168126000` type which is a type defined in the SNOMED Clinical Terms ontology. Similarly, cutting and staining is expressed with a PROV activity typed with `obo:OBI_0000372` type referring to an ontology stored in the Linked data server designed for ontologies. The transportation activity is typed with `pbm:transportActivity`. As exact times of some activities end is not always known, the `endTime` property of the particular activity is not present in finalised provenance information.

Each of the activities generate intermediate results, which are used by a consequent activity. The results contain the sample in various stages of its processing. The types and other relevant attributes of the sample are expressed using corresponding PROV entity attributes, similarly to the Biological Material Acquisition bundle. The sample attributes include `prov:type` (to express type of the sample), `cpm:externalId` (to express identifier of the sample), `pbm:hasContainerType` (to express type of container in which the sample is stored), and `pbm:hasPreservation` (to express fixation type of the sample).

Responsibilities for various activities are expressed in the same way as in the Biological Material Acquisition bundle. In particular, the responsibilities for activities are expressed as PROV Agents related to the activities using the PROV Association relation.

The resulting finalised provenance information is depicted in Figure A2.2.

A2.2 Domain specific provenance attached to a provenance backbone for the sample processing step.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824087.

Biological Material Storage

The biological material storage part of the example includes long-term storage of the sample in a biobank, and subsequent distribution of the sample to a user.

The storage starts with the documentation of the receipt of the sample from the pathology department, which is expressed as `pbm:receivementActivity` type of respective activity. The actual storage process is expressed as activity of type `obo:OBI_0000977`. The environment in which the sample is stored is expressed as `pbm:toEnvironment` attribute with the `obo:NCIT_C70719` value. The sample retrieval, processing, and distribution are expressed as activities of type `pbm:retrieval`, `pbm:processingActivity`, and `pbm:distributionActivity`.

Similarly to the previous provenance component, the sample attributes include `prov:type` (to express type of the sample), `cpm:externalId` (to express identifier of the sample), and `pbm:hasPreservation` (to express fixation type of the sample).

The resulting finalised provenance information is depicted in Figure A2.3.

A2.3 Domain specific provenance attached to a provenance backbone for the sample storage.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824087.

Appendix 3 EMBRC Model of Provenance Metadata

The model of provenance metadata that is being created within EMBRC focuses on non-clinical, non-human material *and* its subsequent data. The immediate audience for this model will be the scientists and data managers working at marine stations/institutes/labs. The first use of the model will be within EMBRC's EMO BON¹⁴ project, where the emphasis on data provenance and re-usability is strong. It will also be promoted among EMBRC's partner institutes, whose scientists collect physical material (samples) for subsequent use and for long-term storage (e.g. biobanking), and who publish the data obtained from those samples through community archives such as EurOBIS, EMODnet, PANGAEA, etc. To have discussions with those same community archives about provenance metadata handling in light of this model is also a goal. Finally, part of the model will also deal with the handling of metadata related to the Nagoya Protocol and other legal contracts and permits that are necessary when sampling, processing, and utilising marine biological material. An explanation of the impact of the Nagoya Protocol on the utilisation of sampled material can be found in the report "FAIR Data Management: Provenance and the Nagoya Protocol" which is in the google drive for Task 6.4¹⁵.

In this appendix, we provide a table that maps provenance structure types defined in the EMBRC provenance model to the CPM and the general Biological Material Provenance types (Section 3).

The EMBRC provenance model is a work in progress, not yet even having a first version release. This documentation of this initial version can be found on <https://github.com/emo-bon/provenance-model-docs>.

This mapping table was created on the 19th of July 2023.

D6.6	D6.6 Semantics	EMBRC	EMBRC semantics
bpm:sample	a PROV entity that represents a biological or environmental sample.	TBC	
bpm:container	a PROV entity that represents a container.		
bpm:device	a PROV entity that represents a processing or storage device for specimen.	Instrument	
bpm:reagent	a PROV entity that represents a reagent.		
bpm:sop	a PROV entity that represents a standard operating procedure.	Protocol	

¹⁴ <https://www.embrc.eu/services/emo-bon>

¹⁵ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xbKDHErpiZO6HTM2dsglp52tMttTduNV>

bpm:source	a PROV entity that represents a source of a sample.	TBC	
bpm:distributionActivity	a PROV activity that represents distribution or disposal of a sample.	<i>Distribution is part of Transport</i>	
bpm:retrievalActivity	a PROV activity that represents retrieval of a sample from sample storage.	<i>Retrieval is part of Transport and Storage</i>	
bpm:storageActivity	a PROV activity that represents storage of a sample.	Storage (spec. of Physical Activity)	Putting the material in a place for an amount of time, usually at a certain temperature and in some kind of container
		Biobanking (spec. of storage)	The storing of material for the long term, with the intention that it can be made available upon request. We are agnostic to who or where that material is stored: this can be a biobank or culture collection facility, or the long-term storage in a lab/marine station.
processingActivity	a PROV activity that represents processing of a sample	Processing (spec. of Physical Activity)	Any work done on the samples that change those samples in some way, e.g. adding chemicals such as preservatives, filtering, centrifuging, cutting up, etc.
receivmentActivity	a PROV activity that represents reception of a sample	<i>Receivment is part of Transport</i>	
transportActivity	a PROV activity that represents transport of a sample	Transport (spec. of Physical Activity)	Mainly intended to cover posting or shipping of material, e.g. from the lab to a processing centre via an agent. It can also cover sending material from the field to the lab: that activity can better be covered by the class Storage, unless this also involves an (external) agent
		Acquisition (spec. of	Acquiring physical material (e.g. sampling, experimentation)

acquisition Activity	a PROV activity that represents acquisition of a sample	Physical Activity)	
		Sampling (spec. of Acquisition)	Extracting material from “the field”
		Ordering (spec. of Acquisition)	Ordering material from a collection (e.g. culture collection, biobank, your own lab’s storage)
		Physical Activity (spec. of Activity) (<i>is an abstract class</i>)	Any activity that deals with physical material
		Digital Activity (spec. of Activity) (<i>is an abstract class</i>)	Any activity involving digital data
		Quality Control (spec. of Digital Activity)	Performing checks on data to ensure completeness, correctness: quality
		Software Processing (spec. of Digital Activity)	Any processing of data, be that simple mathematical calculations or manipulations done in excel or more complex processing via software and workflows; note that this will include software that are included within instruments that do physical processing of material
		Data Retrieval (spec. of Digital Activity)	Obtaining data from another digital source, e.g. an online catalogue or a colleague’s spreadsheet

Table 4: A Mapping of the EMBRC provenance metadata model to the Biological Material Provenance Information types defined in this deliverable.

Each class/entity of the EMBRC provenance metadata model has a set of metadata/attributes which are outlined in the model. At present, the semantics of these metadata have not been aligned with any specific ontology. Examples of these metadata fields are Location, Agent, Protocol, Permit, or Instrument.

